

APPLICATION OF A BIOMEDICAL TECHNOLOGY- BASED COVERING MATERIAL TO EXPERIMENTAL PURULENT WOUNDS

Abdusalomov B.A.

Aripova S.F.

Ergashev U.Y.

Iriskulov B.U.

Seomashko N.Y.

Xegay L.N.

Tashkent State Medical University

Institute of the Chemistry of Plant Substances of the

Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for
Mental Health

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19690160>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 16th April 2026

Accepted: 18th April 2026

Online: 21st April 2026

KEYWORDS

model of a purulent wound, fillalbin, gel-like collagen, biomedical engineering, pathomorphological examination, Van Gieson

ABSTRACT

Currently, purulent wounds occur in 30-35% of the world's population (WHO, 2024). This disease should be mentioned as an independent disease, not against the background of another disease. Therefore, in this article, we created a model of the purulent wound in the soft tissues between the shoulder blades of the experimental rats and applied it to the purulent wound using a gel-like collagen coating with fillalbin, developed based on domestic biomedical engineering, and observed its effect on regenerative and reparative functions in dynamics using a pathomorphological method. In all groups of rats, a biopsy was taken from the purulent wound tissue on the 7th and 10th day, and the cellular-fibrous architectonics of the connective tissue were determined.

Objective: To analyze the reparative function of the results of treating a purulent wound in the soft tissues of rats with phyllalbin gel-like collagen under experimental conditions using pathomorphological studies.

Materials and methods. Experimental studies were conducted on 170 outbred white male rats, weighing 190–240 g, housed in the Tashkent Medical Academy (TMA) vivarium. We created a model using our proposed method (Ergashev U.Y., Abdusalomov B.A. "A Method for Experimental Modeling of Purulent Wounds." Rationalization Proposal. Certificate No. 1394) and divided the experimental animals into 3 groups: Group 1 (control group) involved the creation of an experimental model of a purulent soft tissue wound; Group 2 (comparison group) received conventional combination therapy (Levomekol – "NIZHPHARM," Russia) alongside the creation of the experimental purulent wound model; Group 3 (main group) involved the creation of the experimental purulent wound model and was treated with conventional therapy plus a gel-like collagen containing phyllalbin. On the 7th and 10th days,

biopsies were taken from the purulent wound tissue of each group and examined using pathomorphological methods.

Results. In the primary group of rats treated with the collagen fillalbin gel form, the tissue of the interscapular purulent wound showed the first signs of tissue regeneration 7 days after treatment. A high degree of changes associated with tissue healing and regeneration was observed in the wound area. To analyze the pathohistological state of the purulent tissues of the main group of rats with a purulent wound process on the 7th day of treatment with a collagen gel form using Van Gieson dye, the following changes can be noted: the structure of the collagen fibers reached maturity. In some places, they are immature, with weakly oriented fibers, indicating an early process of connective tissue formation, but the amount of cells and fluid in the intercellular space has decreased. In some areas, active growth of new vessels (angiogenesis) is observed, which confirms the process of regeneration with synthesis, and the formation of granulation tissue has a high trend. This is also a sign that the gel form of fillalbin-containing collagen acts to accelerate tissue regeneration by stimulating blood supply. It is evident that collagen fibers participate in the process of strengthening tissue structures. However, in some parts of the gel, signs of its complete decomposition can be seen, which reflects the fact that the material's absorption process has reached a high level. It can be seen that significant changes in the cellular composition of the tissue, as well as in the area of tissue regeneration, have been completed in the model of purulent wounds in rats of the main group treated using the gel form of collagen with fillalbin for 10 days of our study. Significant changes in collagen fibers were observed in all tissues, as confirmed by Van Gieson staining. Increased collagenation is observed in the affected area, manifesting as intensive red staining of the collagen fibers. At the same time, the structure of these fibers appears more orderly and less chaotic than in the early stages of recovery. Specifically, collagen fibers are formed in the form of dense fibrils, indicating the final stage of scarring. The environment around collagen fibers is characterized by the presence of fibroblasts and inflammatory cells, such as macrophages and lymphocytes. With tissue regeneration, the number of these cells decreases significantly. This indicates the transition of acute inflammation into a more chronic stage, which is characteristic of improved recovery. Active blood circulation is observed, and the number of native formations near the wound area has increased. Many new capillaries, as well as vessels containing red blood cells, indicate that blood supply has been restored. When comparing the image data with samples on day 7, we can see that the wound has healed on day 10, and we confirm this. With fillalbin, collagen exhibits more pronounced and effective collagenization, indicating progressive recovery. On the 10th day of treatment using the collagen gel form of fillalbin, we observed that collagenation reached its final stage and tissue recovery improved significantly compared to previous stages.

Conclusion. As a result of treatment with fillalbin gel-like collagen, especially as a result of the antiseptic and bactericidal effect of fillalbin in its composition, stabilization of dystrophic and destructive changes in the parts of the purulent wound parenchyma was observed on the 7th day. On the 10th day, due to connective tissue activity in the tissue of the purulent wound, it manifested as the regeneration of collagen, reticulin, and elastin fibers in the form of hyperplasia and hyperchromasia

References:

- 1.Абидова А.Д., Цеомашко Н.Е., Арипова С.Ф. Получение компонентов для раневых покрытий и оценка их биологической активности // Universum: Химия и биология : электрон. научн. журн. 2019. № 11(65). URL: <http://7universum.com/ru/nature/archive/item/7904>.
- 2.Аралова, М.В. Лечение трофических язв нижних конечностей гидроактивными раневыми покрытиями / М.В. Аралова // Вестник новых медицинских технологий. – 2019. – Т. 20. – № 2. – С. 25–28.
- 3.Нишантаев, М. К., Зохилов, А. Р., & Хужамуродова, Г. П. (2025). ОЦЕНКА УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ К ГИПОКСИИ ПРИ АЛЛОКСАНОВОМ ДИАБЕТЕ. Zamonaviy tibbiyot jurnali (Журнал современной медицины), 11(4), 754-764.
- 4.Эргашев, У. Ю., Зохилов, А. Р., & Истамов, М. И. (2025). СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К КОМПЛЕКСНОМУ ЛЕЧЕНИЮ ЭРИТЕМАТОЗНО-БУЛЛЕЗНОЙ ФОРМЫ РОЖИ У БОЛЬНЫХ: ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И НЕДОСТАТКИ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ). Zamonaviy tibbiyot jurnali (Журнал современной медицины), 11(4), 765-775.
- 5.Abdusalomov B. A. The Role of Collagen in The Mechanisms of Chronic Wound Healing for Diabetic Foot Syndrome //Texas Journal of Medical Science. – 2023. – Т. 26. – С. 86-94.
- 6.Abdusalomov, B. A. (2023). The Role of Collagen in The Mechanisms of Chronic Wound Healing for Diabetic Foot Syndrome. Texas Journal of Medical Science, 26, 86-94.
- 7.Ergashev, U. Y., Iriskulov, B. U., Abdusalomov, B. A., & Zohirov, A. R. (2026). YIRINGLI JARONATLARNI BIOTIBBIY HUYAYRALI QOPLOVCHI MATERIAL BILAN DAVOLASH SAMARADORLIGINI DIANAMIKADA VAHOLASH: BAKTERIOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR ASOSIDA. Zamonaviy tibbiyot jurnali (Журнал современной медицины), 13(1), 501-508.
- 8.Ergashev, U. Y., Malikov, N. M., Yakubov, D., Abdusalomov, B., & Gafurov, B. (2023). Use of Collagen and Fibroblasts in Modern Medicine. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 17, 78-84.
- 9.Ergashev. U.Y., Abdusalomov B.A. Experimental modeling of a purulent wound. (2024). International Journal of Medical Sciences, 4(11), 122-128.
- 10.Yusufjanovich, E. U., Rafiqovich, Z. A., & Irsalievich, E. K. (2023). Assessment of the process of epithelialization after complex treatment of diabetic foot syndrome. Texas Journal of Medical Science, 16, 19-23.